

Infodemic & Social Media: Coronavirus Information Access in Gaza City

(A dissertation submitted to the **Department of Mass Communication and Journalism, Tezpur University** in partial fulfilment of the academic requirements for the Degree in Master of Arts with specialisation in Mass Communication and Journalism)

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Declaration

I do hereby declare that the dissertation having the title **“Infodemic and Social Media: Coronavirus Information Access in Gaza City”**, submitted to Tezpur University in partial fulfilment of the requirements of the Degree of Masters in Arts in Mass Communication and Journalism under the School of Humanities and Social Sciences, is a result of my own study and research and that it has not been submitted to any other institution, including this University, in any form, or published at any time before.

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Certificate

This is to certify that the dissertation having the title “**Infodemic and Social Media: Coronavirus Information Access in Gaza City**” submitted to the School of Humanities and Social Sciences, Tezpur University, in partial fulfillment for the award of the degree of Masters in Arts in Mass Communication and Journalism, is a record of research work carried out by Mr. Mohammed M. A. Abunahel, under my supervision and guidance.

All help received by him from various sources have been duly acknowledged.

No part of this thesis has been submitted elsewhere for the award of any other degree.

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Abstract

Coronavirus is without a doubt a global crisis and has been since its outbreak. Its impact has affected many sectors, including media and journalism in almost all the nations of the world. It is significant to study the dynamics of information consumption during the crisis. This study aims to understand how easy it is for people in Gaza to obtain reliable and accurate information and to understand it. The study is based on an online survey with 349 respondents. The findings suggest that there are three different groups of people who contribute coronavirus news and information: influential people/opinion leaders; arbitrary-sharing consumers and non-sharing consumers. Various Palestinian sources along with the Palestinian Ministry of Health (MOH) are reliable sources from which to seek coronavirus news and information, in addition to the Palestinian Press Briefings. People seek COVID-19 news to get more information about the virus; to understand the disease and prevent it, and to transfer and share coronavirus news. Results also show that sociodemographic factors such as age, gender, education, equalisation and experience affect the online users' gratification sought at the time of corona crisis. People in Gaza city are active media users and always share news, and they are interested in coronavirus news and information.

Keywords

Gaza; social media; coronavirus; Infodemic; news consumption.

Introduction

Since the outbreak and spread of coronavirus, which is known as COVID-19, and when the World Health Organization (WHO) recognized it as a pandemic state, the world has reached a dangerous stage of extremely large amounts of misinformation and disinformation about coronavirus. This misinformation is spreading rapidly through social media platforms and other outlets. On 15 February 2020, at the Munich security conference, the WHO Director-General Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus described the news that surrounds coronavirus as 'infodemic', when he clearly said that "we are not just fighting an epidemic; we are fighting an infodemic" ([Tedros, 2020](#)).

An enormous volume of news and information is being dumped on social media platforms such as YouTube, Facebook and Twitter around COVID-19. This has led the WHO to adopt the term 'infodemic'¹, to highlight how much fake news, low quality and ambiguous news ([Nielsen et al., 2020](#)), is being spread intentionally and unintentionally. This transfer from the traditional news paradigm profoundly effects the framing of narratives and the construction of social perceptions ([Schmidt et al., 2017](#)); it also impacts and influences political communication and policy-making, as well as the evolution of public debate ([Starnini et al., 2016](#)), especially when issues are globally controversial ([Del Vicario et al., 2016](#)).

¹ According to the Google Scholar website, the term infodemic had not been widely used before 2020 in academic research. The term 'infodemic' was coined by WHO to illustrate the dangers of the misinformation phenomenon that is surrounding COVID-19 since its outbreak. The portmanteau of infodemic was used in a newspaper in 2003 by David J. Rothkopf to describe 'information epidemics'. The process of blending the term came from 'information + epidemic', to show an uncontrolled state of information, misinformation, or disinformation that is concerned about an issue which makes the solution more complicated.

By applying U&G theory in this study, we intend to explore the preferred websites and social media platforms which are used to get information about coronavirus and the reasons why the people prefer them in Gaza City? Also, the data is collected to understand and analyse the different sources and platforms that aim to spread news and information about coronavirus; how the people in Gaza access news and information; which sources they can rely on to get trusted information and how much misinformation around coronavirus is available on social media platforms. What is the role of social media in disseminating news of the Coronavirus in the Gaza Strip and what are the sources of Coronavirus news in the Gaza Strip; and how do people deal with press briefings and what is its impact on the public; how do people deal with misleading news about coronavirus?

Nowadays, we are in a social media era; therefore, many people depend totally on social media for social interaction; information seeking; to pass the time; or for entertainment. Online users are exposed to news while they are using any social media platform, since all news companies use social media platforms as a hub to publish their news. Exposure to news while using social media is different from one user to another, depending on age, gender, education, or work experience; it might depend on another scale such as the duration of using social media per day, the preferred social media platforms, or the preferred sources they might follow.

The COVID-19 epidemic has become a globally critical issue; its impact can be seen in everyone's life by the way the news and the information are consumed. The information that is available on social media can strongly influence and shape people's behavior. COVID-19 has developed quickly into a pandemic, and the misinformation about it followed a similar exponential growth trajectory.

This paper explores how the people in Gaza City deal with the misinformation about Coronavirus, whether they share the news with fact-checking or without it; their measurements and techniques to stop disseminating of misinformation about coronavirus

The Gaza Strip is considered one of the most densely populated regions in the world ([Abuhabib et al., 2020](#)); The Gaza strip has been placed under a suffocating siege imposed by Israel, the U.S., and other countries, which has led to an international economic and political boycott of Israel since the summer of 2007 ([Shaban, 2017](#)). This brutal siege affects many different sectors, including the health sector through a severe shortage of medications, medical materials and other necessities. Today, Gaza City, with approximately 2 million inhabitants, is facing COVID-19. The Palestinian government responded directly to the pandemic and took strict closure measures to prevent its rapid spread; it also focused on social spacing, personal hygiene, control of border crossings and health preparedness.

Furthermore, the Ministry of Health- Gaza, through its institutions, attaches special importance to preventive and public awareness programs. It has launched several prevention campaigns against the disease, including workshops, science lectures, training sessions and daily press briefings² to educate the people to combat coronavirus ([Health, July, 2020](#)).

The process of disseminating news and information between people is different regarding the issue; sharing news on social media has an influence on individuals ([Lee et al., 2011, September 7-9](#)) as well as society. Individuals can be involved in the production and diffusion of news in large global virtual

² Palestinian news briefing sources (a news press briefing delivered by Eyad Al-Bozom, the Interior Ministry spokesman; Dr Ashraf Al-Qudra, spokesperson of the Ministry of Health in Gaza and Salama Marouf, chairman of the media office. They aim to keep the Gazans updated about the coronavirus situation in Gaza city, and to provide them with the required measure to protect themselves.)

communities ([Lee & Ma, 2012](#)). Facebook nowadays is the most popular social media platform, and it allows its users exposure to news and information either through linking to a news organization's pages, or through Facebook friends who share or write news content; this is a unique feature of news delivery on Facebook ([Turcotte et al., 2015](#)).

During this pandemic, people are focusing on getting news and sharing it with their acquaintances; this sharable information might be misinformation. Online users who share the information are different, based on why they share coronavirus news. So, the categories of consumers of coronavirus news are not the same.

During this deadly pandemic, it is vital that all people receive accurate and timely information. Our goals are to determine if the people in Gaza are able to receive that information in a timely manner; to study the online behaviours of the people of Gaza City during the coronavirus pandemic; to understand the knowledge and the awareness about the credibility of the content on social media, to study the role of people in disseminating coronavirus news; and to examine the different categories of consumers who consume news related to coronavirus. Furthermore, this will help to understand the accessibility of accurate and timely information about the coronavirus for the people of Gaza and will assist in bridging any gaps that may exist, so the people there can protect themselves as well as possible under the circumstance in which they live.

We hope that this analytical study will be useful to the news media, governments, journalists, and to the Gazan people as they learn to distinguish accurate information from misinformation around coronavirus on social media platforms in the Gaza Strip.

Literature review

Since the COVID-19 epidemic has become a globally critical issue, researchers focused on it and on its different aspects. We found limited related studies on the coronavirus situation in Gaza City, the role of the government in containing the virus, the role of The Palestinian Ministry of Health-Gaza, and how the governmental media and public relations deal with the current pandemic. So, we linked our study to other studies that have been done on the same topic. Additionally, we applied the Use and Gratification theory (UAG). This is a common theory that is used to explain the functionality of certain media for their audience and why these media are preferred by that audience.

Prior studies have been carried out to investigate the distribution and themes of infodemics on social media in many countries. For instance, Kouzy et al., ([2020b](#)) assessed the source characteristics of the COVID-19 infodemic being spread on Twitter. They analyze Twitter accounts and post characteristics by applying descriptive statistics. They found that 19.2% of misinformation posts regarding the COVID-19 epidemic was posted by verified Twitter users' accounts, and 66% was posted by unverified individual or group accounts. Moreover, they indicated that the COVID-19 infodemic is being propagated at an alarming rate on social media

Social media platforms are the easiest and most effective ways to disseminate information ([Rempfer, 2017](#)); they have been widely used as sources of information in the world and a large number of registered users on these platforms. However, there are multiple advantages and disadvantages that must be considered. González-Padilla & Tortolero-Blanco, ([2020](#)) studied the advantages and the disadvantages of social media use, and the Infodemic and disinformation of coronavirus news.

Today, social media has some characteristics which can't be found on other media such as television, radio or the newspaper; these characteristics of new media include the creation of content and the ability to share the content immediately. In this respect, researchers have often grouped media gratifications into two categories: process and content ([Kayahara & Wellman, 2007](#)). Social media refers to websites, applications or any digital tools that are designed to allow users to stay connected with family, friends, colleagues or customers; to construct a public or semi-public profile within a bounded system ([Boyd & Ellison, 2007](#)); to allow the creation and exchange of the created content ([Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010](#)); to allow people to share content quickly with each other and to view their list of connections and those made by others within the system ([Boyd & Ellison, 2007](#)).

There are thousands of people spreading information, rumours, sensationalism, disinformation and misinformation, making it crucial for Governments and experts to fight the Infodemic as well as the pandemic. Brindha et al. ([2020](#)) studied the social media reigned by Information or misinformation about COVID-19; they tried to discover whether social media is informing or misinforming the audience in terms of COVID-19.

During the pandemic, most people exposed to social media ([Hussain, 2020](#)). Cinelli et al. ([2020](#)) addressed the diffusion of information about the COVID-19 on social media. They identified information spreading from questionable sources, finding different volumes of misinformation in each platform. A comparative analysis of users' activity on social media platforms has been done during the COVID-19 pandemic. The paper was concluded by computing rumours' amplification parameters for social media platforms.

While Lee and Ma ([2012](#)) investigated the influences of information seeking, socializing, entertainment, and status seeking by applying the UGT and social cognitive theories (SCT). Sharing news activities plays a vital role in the current media environment and in the greater society as well. The dissemination of information can strongly influence people's behavior. Picone et al. ([2016](#)) revealed that people are more motivated to share information because of social connections than because of self-presentation.

Misinformation about COVID-19 on Twitter has been widely studied ([Shahi et al., 2020](#); [Sharma et al., 2020](#); [Singh et al., 2020](#)). Similarly, the COVID-19 Infodemic on Facebook have been also studied ([Ahmed et al., 2020](#); [Guarino et al., 2021](#); [Wang et al., 2020](#); [Yang et al., 2020](#)), as well as on YouTube ([Hernández-García & Giménez-Júlvez, 2020](#); [Knuutila et al., 2020](#); [Li et al., 2020](#); [Serrano et al., 2020](#)).

As we speak of studies on covid-19 and social media, various studies that used Uses and Gratifications theory (UGT) are very pertinent to review. It is an approach to understanding why and how people actively seek out specific media to satisfy specific needs. It is very significant to apply the UGT because of its roots and origins in the communication sciences ([Whiting & Williams, 2013b](#)). Social media sites and platforms are a communication mechanism that gives an individual a space to communicate with thousand or Millions of people all over the world ([Williams et al., 2012](#)). This theory has particular relevance in media and social media. The main premise of UGT is that people adopt specific media to fulfil their needs among many choices of media ([Weaver Lariscy et al., 2011](#)).

This theory is helpful in understanding the motivation of the people for media use; it has been used to investigate the use of mass media ([Kang & Atkin, 1999](#); [Towers, 1987](#)) . UGT is one of the valuable

theories to examine social media. Furthermore, it has been applied on the Internet ([Ruggiero, 2000](#); [Stafford et al., 2004](#)) and also now to social media ([Chen & Chan, 2017](#); [Ku et al., 2013](#); [Li et al., 2017](#); [Luo et al., 2011](#)), or even to specific social networking sites like Twitter, YouTube, Facebook, Pinterest, etc.

After extensive reviewing of the literature, the gap was identified. It might be noticed that all the studies that have been conducted have studied the misinformation, disinformation and Infodemic of coronavirus. No study has been conducted to study the how the online users consider the information that available on social media; how do people deal with misleading news about coronavirus. Since this study is the first study conducted on Gaza City, the study of the Palestinian press briefings is the first study examine the impact of press briefings on the public. This paper also comes to study the categories of consumers of coronavirus news. In the current scientific literature, the consumers of coronavirus news have not been an area of study so far. This evaluation corresponds to the main contribution of this paper. After systematically reviewing the literature regarding the misinformation about coronavirus on social media, we describe the methodology and data employed in our analyses.

Research Methods

In this section we will disuses the methods that has been employed to conduct the study. This report adopted online survey of the people in Gaza City; it was helpful during the pandemic of social media users. Stimson ([2014](#)) believes that an online survey is an affordable method of collecting information from online members. The online survey was conducted in late June and early July 2020. The survey was designed in a way that assured that the purpose of this study is at centre. This study employs

survey method for the collection of the data which is quantitative in nature. Some of the data is analysed through the frame of U&G theory. The survey questions were in the Arabic language and these respondents were all Arabic speakers. The questions and responses were translated into English by the authors to serve the research aims.

The sample of this study is comprised of 349 participants with different ages who took part in the online survey; among the respondents, 188 were women (54%), and 161 were men (46%). The survey was conducted throughout Gaza, being careful to assure that all areas were covered to assure an adequate sample size, and a broad sample. The survey, which comprised 23 mixed questions, took the participants about 8 minutes to complete; the questionnaire was organised in six parts. Part 1 introduction; part 2 sociodemographic profile; part 3 the Usage of Social Media; part 4 misinformation about the COVID-19 Pandemic; part 5 the Palestinian Press Briefings about Coronavirus; and finally, part 6 categories of consumers of coronavirus news.

Theoretical Framework

U&G theory is to explain how and why the audience uses certain mass media in order to fulfil their needs and wants to achieve gratification, and what gratification they receive from it. UGT explores why users use particular media and the outcome of the gratification of usage and access ([Luo et al., 2011](#)). Generally, the focus of the theory is on the user's perspective in selecting a certain media among all available media to satisfy their needs based on the appeal of media content. UGT answers the question "what do people do with media"; it helps to understand how the audience consumes the

media to satisfy their needs. This theory assumes that (a) the audience members are active; (b) media use is aim-directed; (C) media consumption can meet the audience desires and needs to achieve gratification; (d) the audiences have sufficient self-awareness to understand and explain the reasons for their use of the media, and (e) the origins of the gratification exist in the media content and exposure - the social context within which the exposure occurs ([Kaye & Johnson, 2002](#)).

Data analysis and Interpretation

The Demographic Characteristics.

This section analyses the Demographic Characteristics of respondents. The gender and age distribution of the participants was necessary for this study. The analysis of the collected data, as shown in figure 1, presented that 188 (54%) were female, and 161 (46%) were male. Table 1 illustrates the age distribution of the participants among males and females; the result shows that the two largest population were the 26 – 40 year olds, and the less than 25 year olds: 50% of the sampled populations were aged between 26-40 years, and those less than 25 years was 43%. Of the remaining 7%, 5% were 41 – 50 years old, and 2% were more than 51 years old.

Figure 1: Gender distribution of respondents

Table 1: Age distribution of respondents

Age	Female	Male	Total
Less than 25 years	24%	19%	43%
26-40 years	27%	23%	50%
41-50 years	2%	3%	5%
More than 51 years	-	2%	2%

Figure 2 shows the participant's educational qualifications among females and males. The sample was divided into five categories: postgraduate, Bachelor's degree, diploma, secondary and less than secondary. The most common qualifications were Bachelor's degree; females made up 40.4%, and males were 36.6% among all the participants, followed by Secondary school, which represented 26.6% and 24.2, respectively. In the same context, 15.5% of the females and 9.0% of the males held high qualification: master's degree or doctoral degree, while the less common one was less than secondary school.

Figure 2: The educational qualifications among males and females.

In terms of educational experience, figure 3 illustrates that the highest percentage of experience was among the bachelor's degree holders with 39.1%, while the lowest percentage was 3.2% among those who have less than secondary school.

Figure 3: The distribution of educational qualification among the respondents

Q1: what preferred websites and social media platforms are used to get information about coronavirus and why do people prefer them?

We explore in this section the usage of social media during the time of COVID-19. The first question in this study asked participants, "How long have you used social media." The majority of participants reported that they have been using social media for five years (73.9%), followed by four years, three years, two years and one year by 10.3%, 8.6%, 3.7%, 3.4%, respectively (Figure 4).

Figure 4: The distribution of educational experience among the respondents

The second question was, "how many hours do you spend daily reading news about COVID-19 using social media platforms." Forty-seven percent did not have any specific time to read about it, and therefore could not identify a number of hours spent daily reading about COVID-19. This was the highest proportion of participants; 24.9% spend less than one-hour getting coronavirus news, while the lowest proportion was 7.7% of the participants who did not show a high interest in coronavirus news, as can be seen in figure 5.

Figure 5: Daily hours of reading coronavirus news and information

Participants in this study were also asked, "where do you get coronavirus news." As shown in figure 6, social media platforms were categorised into the four platforms: the first category includes Facebook, Twitter, Instagram and YouTube; the second category consists of messaging apps such as WhatsApp, Messenger, Skype and Telegram; the third category is the Google search engine; and the last category is news applications. Facebook was the highest platform with 55.3%. Google search engine was also popular among the respondents by 16.9%, followed by Twitter 8.6%. Meanwhile, Instagram, messaging apps, news apps and YouTube by 9.3%, 5.7%, 3.2% and 2.0%, respectively.

Figure 6: Preferred means to get news about coronavirus

In order to understand the different sources that are used among the participants to get COVID-19 news and information, we asked, "what kind of newspapers, magazines, and websites do you prefer to follow in social media to read coronavirus news." The majority reported that they strongly prefer to get news about COVID-19 from Palestinian sources (28.4%), such as Ma'an Network, PSCTV Palestinian Satellite Channel, Al Intifada, Falastini, Al Falastinia, AlQuds Today, Alkofiya and Palestine Live sources. This was followed by the Gazan Sources 23.2%, such as Al Aqsa, Al Quds, Al Kitab, Hona Al Quds and the Palestinian news briefing sources. This is an exciting result; it will unpack in more detail later in question 3. The lowest majority was the Arabic sources including Al Arabiya, Al-Jazeera and Sky News by 5.2% (figure 7)

Figure 7: Preferred social media platforms

Figure 8 illustrates the responses of 349 people to the questions "do you share news in general on your homepage"; and "do you share coronavirus news". Sixty-one and a half percent of the participants share different kinds of news in general, and 45.3% of all participants share coronavirus news and information on their social media accounts, while 30.4% don't share news at all, and 36.7% of all respondents don't share coronavirus news. In contrast, 18.1% don't care about coronavirus news.

Figure 8: Sharing coronavirus news and news in general

With regard the level of education - less than secondary school, secondary school, diploma, bachelor's degree and postgraduate - there is a remarkable variety in the preferred websites to seek information about COVID-19. This includes the Palestinian Ministry of Health, the World Health Organization, friends and family, local agencies, the global news agencies, and official updating websites. For some there is no preferred platform.

Table 2 shows that all the participants with all different qualifications are consuming more information from the Palestinian Ministry of Health by 33.4%, while the World Health Organization

is consumed by 18.1%. The less consuming was from family and friends by 6.2%; it is interesting that participants with postgraduate degrees don't consume any coronavirus news from family and friends.

News source	Less than secondary	Secondary	Diploma	Bachelor's degree	Postgraduate
The Palestinian Ministry of Health	1.4%	7.7%	8.0%	12.9%	3.4%
The World Health Organization	0.3%	6.9%	1.7%	8.3%	0.9%
Official updating websites	-	1.7%	1.7%	3.4%	1.7%
The global news agencies	-	0.6%	0.9%	3.2%	2.3%
The Local agencies	0.3%	6.9%	2.9%	5.2%	1.7%
Friends and family	1.1%	1.4%	2.0%	1.7%	-
I don't have preferred platforms	-	1.1%	3.2%	4.3%	2.0%

Table 2: Preferred website to get news about COVID-19.

Q2: How do people deal with misleading news about coronavirus?

This section examines if the people in Gaza city help to spread coronavirus news and information.

The first question in this section was "do you check the credibility of the news before sharing it on social media platforms." The goal of this question is to examine whether the people insist on sharing accurate information or not. Figure 9 showed that 86.8% of the responders check the credibility of the news before sharing it on social media or to share the information with other people orally, while 13.2% don't care about the news's credibility.

Figure 9: Check the news credibility

We asked about what Gazan people do when they encounter what they think is misinformation about coronavirus on social media sites. The aims are not only to test people's ability to detect misinformation, but also to understand the various strategies and techniques that the online users apply when they face what they see is misinformation. The results, shown in figure 10, indicate that the majority of 70.8% ignore the misinformation.

The other option was that the users block the account which is trying to spread misinformation about COVID-19: 2.9%. However, 3.7% of the participants would share the news without ensuring its credibility, while 10.9% unfollow the account. Unsurprisingly, 11.7% of the participants would report the account for sharing misinformation.

Figure 10: The measure to stop COVID-19 spreading

To survey the pervasiveness of false information and misinformation regarding COVID-19, we asked the people who took part in questionnaires about the frequency with which they face what they perceived as misinformation about the COVID19 pandemic (Figure11).

The general trend was "sometimes" by 58.2%, followed by the second trend, "most of the time" by 28.4%, while the third trend was "always" by 8.6%. Interestingly, in our sample, people by 4.9%, "never" encounter COVID-19 misinformation

Figure 11: The frequency of encountering misinformation

We asked the participants "How much do you trust the accuracy of news about the COVID-19 pandemic on social media platforms" as shown in figure 12. Only a half of the respondents trust the accuracy of news and information around coronavirus (50.1% trusted a moderate amount), while a "little" made up only 30.4%, and 10.3% have "a great deal" of trust. The lowest majority don't trust anything related to COVID-19 at all.

Figure 12: Trust the accuracy COVID-19 news

Q3: What is its impact of press briefings on the public?

In February 2020, the first initial committee was established to follow up on the coronavirus situation in the Gaza strip; to monitor international developments about the pandemic; to allocate quarantine centres for returnees from the affected countries and to propose the necessary measures in this field.

Since March 15, 2020, all travellers coming through Rafah and Beit Hanoun (Erez) crossings had to undergo a compulsory quarantine at one of the MoH designated facilities.

We asked the participants three questions in this section about the Palestinian news-press briefings, which were delivered mainly by the ministry of health. The goals of this section are to examine how frequently people follow ministry activities and how they interact with it.

The first question was "Do you follow the official page of the Palestinian Ministry of Health on social media platforms." As shown in figure 13, among all participants, 22.9% follow the official pages of Palestinian Ministry of Health-Gaza on social media platforms, while 77.1% don't follow their pages.

Figure 13: Follow the Health Ministry- Gaza on social media

The second question asked the participants, "How do you follow the Palestinian news-press briefing about coronavirus COVID-19." Figure 14 illustrates how people follow the Palestinian news-press briefing about coronavirus. All the respondents showed a high interest in the Palestinian news-press briefing: 39.3% irregularly follow the Palestinian news-press, and more interestingly, 20.1% follow it regularly – daily. Furthermore, 25.5% of the participants read the news and the headlines about it on social media platforms, while the lowest number was 2.3% of the respondents who don't care about it and 12.9% don't follow it.

Figure 14: The frequency following the Palestine news-press briefings

The third question was, "do you share the Palestinian news-press briefing of COVID-19 on your homepage." The responses indicate that 62.8% of the participants do share the news-press briefing, while 37.2% did not show a high interest in sharing it (Figure 15).

Figure 15: Share Palestinian news-press briefings

Q4: What are the different categories of consumers who consume news related to coronavirus?

In the last section, we tried to determine the possibility of identifying various kinds of people who are interested in coronavirus news and information. We aimed to understand how they can play an essential role in public opinion and to understand how people try to get the message out to the community throughout their social media platforms or even through person to person communication. Our focus here is to quantify these people, and to see whether they are active in the time of the pandemic, how they have influenced information propagation in social media and the factors that affect and shape their behaviours.

When asked about why they are so interested in COVID-19 news, the high majority of those sampled are interested in coronavirus news and information to understand the disease and prevent it (64%), while the lowest number is 6% of those who are interested in transferring and sharing the coronavirus news. (Figurer 16)

Figure 16: Reasons for exposure to coronavirus news

Participants in this study were also asked: "are you contributing to the spread of COVID-19 news among family, friends, and co-workers". Figure 17 shows that 58.2% share the news if they have a

piece of accurate news; in this case, the news becomes sharable. Twenty-two percent don't share the news even if the news is accurate and precise, while 19.2% don't share the news whether it's true or not.

This result may suggest that there is a difference in a contribution of coronavirus news and information by people: influential people/opinion leaders (who aim to contribute coronavirus news and information when they have accurate news, and who have an impact on or shape how people act, and have the ability to convince others to listen and do what they suggest); arbitrary-sharing consumers (they are interested in coronavirus news, and they share any coronavirus news and information, without fact-checking, or caring of its effects); non-sharing consumers, (they might be interested coronavirus news or nor, or they might be readers of coronavirus news or not, but they don't share any coronavirus news and information at all).

Figure 17: The contributing of coronavirus news by people

Here, we examine how many people surrounding the influential people/opinion leaders, non-sharing consumers, and arbitrary-sharing consumers, and how many times they are exposed to coronavirus news. People are more likely to be exposed to coronavirus news and information from family, friends,

and co-workers. The results have been divided into two main questions; each question has a different scale, as can be seen in table 3.

The result demonstrated that the influential people/opinion leaders' group was the highest of all groups who aim to contribute coronavirus news and information when they have accurate news. Our study showed that 20.1% of influential people/opinion leaders had from six to ten people in their work or residential area sharing coronavirus news. They are exposed to COVID-19 news and information from one to five times a day by 21.2%. The lowest amount was from one to three people per day (9.6%) and they were exposed from five to ten times a day, also the lowest amount (12.3%).

The arbitrary-sharing consumers' group was the lowest group among other groups who share any coronavirus news and information, whether the news is accurate or not. The highest amount on the scale is from one to three people (7.6%), and they receive it most often: from ten times and more per day (13.7%). Whereas the lowest amount was from ten people and more (2.1%), and the lowest scale was one to five times a day (5.3%).

In the same context, non-sharing consumers who may or may not be interested in coronavirus news and information, and do not share any COVID-19 news, are exposed to COVID-19 news by from one to three people a day (7.7%). The lowest scale of people was from six to ten people a day (2.1%). The highest scale (number of times news about coronavirus was received) was from five to ten times a day (14.8%), and the lowest scale was one to five times a day (6.8%).

Table 3: The factors and scales that shape the people.

Questions	Variable	Non-sharing consumers	Arbitrary-sharing consumers	Influential people/opinion leaders
How many times have you received news about the coronavirus from friends, family members and co-workers?	One to five times a day	6.8%	5.3%	21.2%
	Five to ten times a day	14.8%	6.2%	12.3%
	More than 10 times a day	7.2%	13.7%	12.5%
How many friends, family members and co-workers are trying to spread news about the coronavirus in your work and residential area?	Less than 3 people	7.7%	7.6%	9.6%
	From 3 to 6 people	5.2%	3.2%	16.8%
	From 6-10 people	2.1%	2.7%	20.1%
	More than 10 people	3.4%	2.1%	16.5%

We explored what people do when they receive news and information about the coronavirus COVID-19 from family, friends, and co-workers. Figure 18 represents that 52.1% check the reliability and the credibility of the news after receiving it from other people, followed by 37.8% who keep the information for themselves (they don't share the news at all with other people), while 10.1% pass the news to other people without making sure of its credibility.

Figure 18: Check the news credibility

Table 4 indicates that many factors might affect and shape the attitudes of people to be non-sharing consumers, influential people/opinion leaders, or arbitrary-sharing consumers; these factors include gender, age, qualification and experience. In general, the influential people/opinion leaders' group was the highest among females between the ages of 40 to 50 years with a bachelor's degree, and experience with more than 20 years by 30.3%, 19.2%, 12.9%, and 16.6%, respectively. This finding suggests that influential people/opinion leaders are educated, older and have more than 20 years of experience.

The arbitrary-sharing consumers group was the lowest group compared with non-sharing consumers and influential people/opinion leaders. Arbitrary-sharing consumers are less educated with less than secondary school (only 9.1% have secondary school). They have less than five years of experience

(6.2%), and their ages are less than 25 years (5.2%). While the non-sharing consumers were high in their education in bachelor's degree (9.1%), their ages were more than 50 years (6.4%).

Table 4: Factors that affect and shape the people

Factors	Variables	Non-sharing consumers	Arbitrary-sharing consumers	Influential people/opinion leaders
Gender	Female	9.5%	10.2	30.3%
	Male	13.3%	9.0%	27.6%
Age	Less than 25 years	5.9%	5.2%	14.3%
	25-40 years	5.7%	4.7%	14.1%
	40-50 years	2.9%	2.9%	19.2%
	More than 50 years	6.4%	0.0%	18.7%
Qualification	Less than secondary	3.6%	9.1%	1.8%
	Secondary	4.6%	3.3%	12.1%
	Diploma	3.9%	4.2%	11.8%
	Bachelor's degree	9.1%	3.5%	12.9%
	Postgraduate	7.3%	4.3%	8.5%
Experiences	Less than 5 years	3.4%	6.2%	15.6%
	From 5 to 10 years	6.2%	5.1%	13.8%
	From 10 to 15 years	10.7%	3.4%	10.7%
	More than 20 years	3.7%	4.6%	16.6%

Discussion

The present work provides a first snapshot of the online behaviors of the people of Gaza City during the coronavirus pandemic. The uses and gratifications theory has been useful in our study to examine why people use social media as a means to seek coronavirus news and information during the crisis. The coronavirus pandemic represents a social, health, and economic challenge, but also an opportunity to study how communication can play an essential role in a time of crisis. It constitutes a portrait of the communicative behavior of people during the crisis in Gaza City, exactly from the time when the World Health Organization declared the virus as global pandemic on 11 March 2020.

Throughout our analysis of this study, we notice that the number of users in social media networking sites are in continuous growth ([Clement, 2020](#)); the number of social media users in Gaza City is also high; people have been using them for a long time despite the blockade-caused electricity problem ([Nassar & Alsadi, 2019](#)). At the same time, Gazan people are interested in coronavirus news and information, but most of them don't have a regular time to acquire the accurate information, but they follow the news and the notification updates regarding the pandemic through different ways: either social media platforms or other media. Our study is clearly in line with earlier research conducted by Mertens et al. ([2020](#)), which has clearly showed that some people constantly follow all news updates regarding the virus. In contrast, some people did not show a high interest about it for reasons which have been discussed by Fullana et al. ([2020](#)). In their study, they see that people avoid coronavirus news to reduce the level of anxiety symptoms. Therefore, reading news bulletins, statistics and updates would increase fear of the virus ([Garfin et al., 2020](#)).

There are ten reasons that people seek gratification through the use of social media: social interaction, information seeking, relaxation, communicatory utility, convenience utility, passing time, entertainment, information sharing, expression of opinion, and surveillance/knowledge about others ([Whiting & Williams, 2013a](#)).

The findings from this study show that people tend to use Facebook more for coronavirus news than any other social media because it is the most popular social media platform used in Gaza City. Two primary needs that motivate people to use Facebook are (1) the need to belong (demographic and cultural factors), and (2) the need for self-presentation, whose factors contribute to self-esteem, shyness, narcissism, self-worth and neuroticism ([Nadkarni & Hofmann, 2012](#)). At the same time, people in Gaza City tend to use Google searches to obtain COVID-19 news and information; these people are more likely to be educated and fully aware of the crisis, and looking for accurate news and information from their origin sources. Using Google searches is free from the social aspect of the search that is inherent in getting COVID-19 information from Facebook ([Lyócsa et al., 2020](#)). At the same time, Gazan people tend also to use YouTube as a source of information; Marchal, Au, & Howard ([2020](#)) reported that YouTube has been used as a main purveyor for online video-sharing during the corona crisis

The findings of this study recognised that the participants trust the Palestinian sources, including Gazan sources, more than other sources; it might indicate that they are interested in what is happening in general in Palestine and specifically in Gaza City; this finding does not agree with Rosengard et al., ([2014](#)) who reported that local news does not seem to carry as much importance as the news on social media. Those who find COVID-19 information in all sources are interested in what is happening in

the world; these people are highly educated, look for more information from different sources, are aware, and insist on getting news and information to obtain more knowledge in order to take required protective measures.

We come to understand the reasons behind the high percentage of sharing news in general among the people in Gaza City; that is due to the brutal actions of Israel against the Palestinian people and the availability of the content on social media about Gaza suffering. However, people in Gaza City use various social media platforms as a means to share what is happening daily in Gaza to let the world know how they are suffering and how they struggle to get their basic needs met. Lee and Ma ([2012](#)) have shown in their study that the informativeness, socializing and status seeking are the gratification factors influencing news sharing intention on social media. Moreover, the people in Gaza have also shown their interest in coronavirus news. This finding agrees with Bright et al. ([2020](#)), in which they reported that the content of health-related news and information is being shared and distributed across networks that have tens of millions of users.

The Palestinian Ministry of Health and The World Health Organization are the top two most used media to seek information related to the pandemic in Gaza City. People with all differences in terms of age, gender, experience and qualifications completely trust and depend on the Palestinian Ministry of Health to get the accurate information of coronavirus, since the virus is surrounded by much misinformation and fake news. The World Health Organization is also in high consumption and is seen to be a trusted source for COVID-19 information; in addition, WHO is well-known as a reputable source of credible and trusted information. Gorter ([2020](#)) reported that the World Health Organization website is a reliable source to obtain coronavirus information.

In contrast of their high interest in the content on social media platforms, people in Gaza City do not believe all content on social media sites because they agree that social media sites help to spread false news ([Vosoughi et al., 2018](#)) as well as accurate news ([Corodeanu, 2015](#)). They trust the content to a moderate degree, which leads to understanding that they have the ability to decide and to distinguish what is accurate what is not. The platforms of social media accelerate spreading news and information about coronavirus; this finding is supported by Kouzy et al., ([2020a](#)) when they found in their study that since the outbreak of coronavirus, the news and information has been spreading uninhibited over social media; one result is that it causes panic among people. The vast amount of information on social media affects its credibility, so some news may mislead the people.

At the same time, due to the huge availability of fake news and misinformation about coronavirus, some people don't trust any content on unofficial pages, and they don't hurry to share any content. This result leads to understanding that people depend on the content itself, their knowledge, and what they have known so far about COVID-19 to decide the credibility of the news that is found on social media.

Massive participation on social media platforms is reflected in the endless number of news items, online posts, and opinions. Social media give users the opportunity to create and share content on their own. This paper's findings indicate that misinformation is spread predominantly online ([Santos Rutschman, 2020](#)), and the high majority of the people in Gaza City do their best to stop spreading any misleading information; the reasons might be because they are educated, they are aware of the pandemic danger, they are precise with the web searches ([Cooper, 2020](#)), or they are getting the

information from different sources, so they have the ability to distinguish between misinformation and accurate information.

The findings of this paper show that people don't engage with what they see if it is misinformation from their respective; this result helps us to understand that that Gazan people are aware of the importance of validating news and information about COVID-19 found on social media and are likely to make the efforts to do so. This finding indicates also that the Gazan people help to stop those who are trying to spread misinformation with the available strategies and techniques which they have, such as blocking or unfollowing the account that is trying to disseminated misinformation. People don't take part in reporting the accounts that spread misinformation to social media companies, although these companies rely on their users to inform them about any content that might be violating their community standards. That is an essential avenue for social media companies to find out an alternative option to stop those people who are trying to mislead other people.

In the age of news accessibility, and where reliable, credible, accurate information is incredibly important from the government to the people, there has to be as a source of news or information about the crisis. We came into an unexpected result: the vast majority of the people don't follow and interact with the official pages of the Palestinian Ministry of Health-Gaza on social media platforms because the ministry is not active on social media platforms. At the time in which we write this paper, the number of followers on the official page of the Palestinian Ministry of Health-Gaza on Twitter did not reach 1,010 followers on the Arabic page, and 622 followers on the English page. Similarly, just 37,220 followers follow the official page of the Palestinian Ministry of Health- Gaza on Facebook; around 560 followers on Instagram, and exactly 369 subscribers on YouTube (Figure 19).

At the same time, the Palestinian Ministry of Health-Gaza is active on their official websites; they regularly keep it updated with the news and their activities. We come to understand that the ministry of health depends on the media houses to deliver their content (news briefings, events etc.) on social media platforms to the public. Hence, people find information on other media houses. More interestingly, people are gathering information from governmental sources: the people in Gaza City show high interest in the Palestinian news-press briefings about coronavirus, and they follow them regularly and irregularly through different media platforms and TV channels. People in the Gaza Strip tend also to read COVID-19 news and information to understand the disease and prevent it, to transfer and share the news about it and to obtain more information about coronavirus.

The research set out to explore different kinds of people who contribute coronavirus news and information. The conclusions obtained from this paper have essential implications for academic research. We reached the results from an analysis of the new three groups of people during corona pandemic.

Influential people/opinion leaders who aim to contribute coronavirus news and information when they have accurate news, and who have an impact on or shape how people act, and have the ability to convince others to listen and do what they suggest. Vinerean et al. ([2013](#)) reached out to four new types of social media consumers: Expressers and Informers, Engagers, Networkers, and Watchers and Listeners. This potential to influence is supported by Quinn ([2020](#)), prior work showing that opinion leaders are disseminating trusted information about COVID-19.

The second group is arbitrary-sharing consumers, those who are interested in coronavirus news, and they share any coronavirus news and information, without fact-checking, or caring of its effects.

The third group is non-sharing consumers, those who might be interested in coronavirus news or not, or they might be readers of coronavirus news or not, but they don't share any coronavirus news and information at all.

This helps us to quantify the effect of these people in information and news dissemination on society by distinguishing between them through their distribution mechanism and their participation in disseminating news and information of COVID-19; this process of disseminating might be through social media platforms or through face to face communication.

We realise that the more people are exposed to coronavirus news and information in terms of the number of people and the frequency of time, the more likely they are to be influential people/opinion leaders. This result may suggest that influential people/opinion leaders, who aim to contribute coronavirus news and information when they have accurate news, are more likely to share COVID-19 news and information because they are exposed to the news and information more than the other groups. It also leads us to conclude that the more received news and information, the more spread of COVID-19 news and the information. Our study concluded that older people and females are more likely to be influential/ opinion leaders; these findings from our study are only partly supported by (Aral and Walker, 2012), who agreed that older people are more influential than younger, but they disagreed regarding the level of influence of women, finding that it is men who are more influential than women. This apparent discrepancy will benefit from further study.

Palestinian Ministry of Health- Gaza

@mohenglish3

Official twitter account of the Palestinian Ministry of Health- Gaza The Public Relationship and the Media Unit

Gaza twitter.com/mohenglish3

Joined July 2018

171 Following 622 Followers

Following

وزارة الصحة - فلسطين

@MOH_PR

رعايتكم الصحية واجب وطني نعتز به - العلاقات العامة والإعلام بوزارة الصحة الفلسطينية

Gaza moh.gov.ps Joined May 2012

149 Following 1,009 Followers

Following

Instagram

Instagram

ministry_of_health_gaza

Message

3 posts

563 followers

11 following

وزارة الصحة الفلسطينية_غزة

YouTube

Ministry of Health

369 subscribers

SUBSCRIBED

Facebook

وزارة الصحة الفلسطينية / غزة

Government Organization

Message

الاعلامى, Em, Osama and 37,217 others like this

Home

Reviews

Photos

Videos

Posts

Commu

Figure 19: The official pages of the Palestinian Ministry of Health -Gaza on social media

Conclusion

Through our paper, the uses and gratifications theory has been useful when we study the news and information seeking during the coronavirus pandemic. This paper demonstrates the different sources that people use in Gaza City to seek coronavirus news and information; the local news "Palestinian sources" such as Ma'an Network, Al Aqsa, Al Quds and Al Kitab are more consumed on social media to obtain the news. People rely on the Palestinian sources to seek the news along with the Palestinian press briefings.

Social media platforms are the main sources for disseminating coronavirus news and information; the people depend on them for news while trying to seek gratification. Social media platforms like Facebook are highly consumed for news-seeking due to its reactivity and its availability everywhere. The flow of infodemic may lead to uncontrolled consequences which induce substantial interruption of social-economic activities, and on the political level.

We took into account the role of different kinds of people in information dissemination during the corona pandemic, which leads us to conclude that there are three different groups: non-sharing consumers, arbitrary-sharing consumers and influential people/opinion leaders.

At the end of this paper, it should be mentioned here the role of the Palestinian government through press briefings, and specifically the role of the Palestinian Ministry of Health to contain the virus by different means regardless of the limitation which they have due to the brutality of Israel siege, and the difficult economic situation. Until now, Gaza City still follows the quarantines and isolations and other measures to prevent any uncontrolled crisis among the citizens.

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